

John Maynard Keynes said “The day is not far off when the economic problem will take the back seat where it belongs, and the arena of the heart and the head will be occupied or reoccupied, by our real problems – the problems of life and of human relations, of creation and behaviour and religion”.

Current situation counts as something on this arena where everything takes backseat and our essentials take the driving seat to keep us alive for every day. And to keep oneself alive Finance is the most important thing to survive

Finance as known to many as the life blood of companies is essential for our daily living just few sectors have been covered to make a better understanding as how India will stand in this post lockdown arena.

1. Problems will persist with realty sector so they will start making mechanics and will depend on lot of mechanised way of building. So a huge upside in next few months for companies involved in cranes, building lifts and other ancillaries.
2. Lockdown will end but social distancing won't so huge scope for many two wheelers company to actually take the benefit of the same.
3. Most Labourers will have to be reskilled as this pandemic will not stop it will keep coming and will hit us so know we have to become used to such situations so companies into healthcare industry are going to be an huge value creation so companies small enterprises in Masks. PPE, HAND GLOVES, SANITIZERS, HANDWASH COMPANY WILL BE IN HUGE DEMAND AS NEXT 8-9 months we will have to use them and could be more.
4. Technology backed company, our education system will change a lot and virtual lectures will be part of life so stocks with such background will be huge and the companies doing their digital security will all the more be relevant.

Few Sectors:

Aviation:

Problems persist as the news rolling, they will not be allowed to book full scale the three seaters economy class will have the middle row seats to be kept empty which will leave them with huge lacuna in their operating margins.

AgroChemicals:

Will be in good shape till a good monsoon is in place and as per the IMD report the monsoon will be a normal so could see an uptick.

Automobile:

Will have problems on multiple counts as the supply chain management will be in problem as an example a leading Car Manufacturing company who has a plant in Haryana get the Materials from Maharashtra, Gujarat, Odisha and many other parts of country. Secondly, the production will start but with no opening of retail sales or what we say it as POS the only production of cars won't help will make matters more worse as the working capital is in pain for most of the Automobile sector.

Banks and Financial Institutions:

Will have trouble at few fronts the 1st being the flow of money from the people to whom loans were disbursed and other is getting the new credit started will be a trouble (even though our interest rates have come down highly).

Hospitality Sector and QSR:

With limited supply of Labour the situation will be in trouble for some time and same like aviation will have to do away with lot of tables and thus restricting their topline.

Branded Clothing and Shoes:

As essential items will take precedence it will be an absolutely difficult for them to come out of woods so early.

Branded Jewellery:

It will be in a problem a gold price heads north wards the sector ill need all the prayers to save itself as the whole of festival season is know over, by the time lockdown comes to an end the monsoon season will set in and will hamper their sales in big time.

Educational Services:

There lies huge potential for companies linked to educational services to upscale their intake and as this will pave way for **Click University from Brick University**, In this time of **Adversity** it will be the **E-Varsity** will be that learners will be looking for, the advantage for this companies will multi-faceted as with technology taking precedence the educators will have to be tutored an then the learners, Government agencies, the Regulatory body, Universities and all the decision makers will have to relook this sector and could be a sunrise sector in coming decade.

Facility Management Services:

The best player in the post lockdown scenario is companies involved in Housekeeping, Security Services, and companies in Manufacturing of Cleaning Equipments

FMCG:

The biggest beneficiary of this pandemic will be to them as essential commodities takes the first place in our kitchen's.

Healthcare, Health Equipment manufacturing and Pharma Sector:

Will be of utmost importance as being the Corona warriors as referred to them they will be an huge Asset as this pandemic will leave a huge scare in the life of many of people and their demands will shoot up like anything.

Insurance Sector:

The sector will have a mixed bag, with more weights being thrown on financial literacy by regulatory bodies and awareness on Life Insurance products and which is visible from our advertising that shows more on Term Insurance the sector will grow 4x than the last decade.

General Insurance sector will be in for a huge potential as more and more corporates, government, private bodies will want to give their employees the benefit of health insurance it will see a huge upswing in the years to come and would be in huge demand.

Infrastructure Sector (Real estate):

The problem will persist for this sector in coming days still reeling with shocks from past 3 to 3 ½ years first with Demonetisation, then RERA, and GST all of this have just been a problem for them and it will take long for the sector to come out of the woods. Just to make matters worse the work from home culture is another nightmare for them as more and more corporates will turn to it and use it to their advantage to reduce their rental cost. With the lockdown to stay more longer and social distancing being the norm it would be very difficult for companies to meet ends unless a strong RITES policy isn't in place.

Information Technology:

This space will spice up as today when the lock down still going on this sector has been responsible to run the wheels of economy especially our whole financial sector has been run by them, Not only financial sector but Educational sector has been also run by the Information & technology sector. New terminologies will keep them running EduTech, FinTech, MediTech will be of utmost importance.

Oil & Gas:

With global oil prices cooling off and at an 18 year low it's good for upstream oil companies like ONGC & Oil India but could spell a nightmare for Downstream Companies those like Oil Marketing Companies like IOC, HPCL & BPCL with demand not there and down nearly by 90% it will be inevitable that these companies have a tight rope to walk and there could be a change in their dividend payout they will have to look to government with some sort of relief bonds.

Print Advertising & Paper Industry:

Print Advertising:

With the subscription seeing a fall of more than 80% the sector will need an external hand and with the slowdown in economy there won't be an immediate uptick in the advertising of companies involved in these sector.

Paper Industry:

With lockdown in place the sector can take solace from the fact that the companies involved in the sector if can change a few production factors and make paper napkins it will be a potential uptick for this sector and could see a re-rating in coming days.

Telecom:

A sector which could be bouncing back will be this sector with average tariff hike in the month of December 2019 and know with average consumption of Data increasing this sector will see a huge growth and with work from home being the norm and continue in the starting of new decade it will be the most profitable sector.

THE GDP MAY GO DOWN AND WOULD BE @1 - 2% but post 9 – 12 months our GDP will bounce back at much faster pace.

As China's quality of production will know be a question mark.

China manufacturing 20% of worlds production so even if we take even half of the same we will be in a better way to compete than what we were before.

India has seen and faced lots of problems and have come triumphs weather it's the

1990 – Balance of Payments crisis

1992 – Babri demolition

1993 – Bombay Bomb Blasts

2000 – Y2K problem

2005 – Mumbai Floods

2007 – Bomb Blasts

2008 – 2012 – Financial Crisis

These are few instances which we have seen over the 4 decades and we have come triumphs the eyes have seen more pains but our eyes have seen the joys and celebration together:

In the winning of 1983 and 2011 Cricket world cup;

The first medal at Olympics in 1996 after a decade and;

Successful, in entering the Mars Orbiter Mission in 2014 being the first country to achieve such feat in its first attempt.

It's this vigour and valor and never give up attitude has stood in trying times and we will overcome this phase of life. ***In the words of, Victor Frankl, author, "The last of human freedoms – the ability to choose one's attitude in a given set of circumstances".***

World will look to India in more positive way and will have more faith on us.

It is a great time for start-up's to up their scale.

- So those who are into business think of ways and means where you can scale up your production.
- Those who are in jobs just hold to it.
- Those who are in stock market search for beaten but with great business models companies.
- Those who are in trading trade with your stop losses.

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